

SOCIAL SCIENCES

SKILLS AND ABILITIES THAT WILL BE FORMED BY MEANS OF TEACHING STUDENTS IN THE PROCESS OF LEARNING SOCIAL WORK

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ABSTRACT

Introduction: The teaching tools include books, pictures, diagrams and other auxiliary items used in the educational process. Textbooks on social work are "tools" of pedagogical work, with the help of which the teacher not only transmits and consolidates knowledge, but also teaches students how to use these tools, forms the ability to work with various sources of social knowledge. Textbooks on social work perform the following tasks: increasing the pedagogical effect of teaching, forming moral education, ensuring the development of students, providing educational material in sufficient volume and depth, as well as developing the ability to work with primary sources and research methods. The main purpose of this article is to analyze and systematize methods and means of teaching social work, as well as to develop recommendations for their improvement.

Relevance: The education of social workers requires the use of a variety of training tools to develop professional skills and abilities. Modern pedagogical approaches require the integration of theoretical knowledge with practical skills, which makes it relevant to analyze and improve the educational tools used.

Novelty: The novelty of the research lies in the systematization of modern teaching methods and tools, as well as in the development of recommendations for their optimization to increase the effectiveness of the educational process in social work.

Research methods: To conduct the research, a detailed analysis of scientific and methodological literature on social work and pedagogy, including works by domestic and foreign authors, was carried out. In particular, the works of Kuzmin and Sutyurin (2003), Şeker (2012), Friedlander (1983), Payne (2005), Fook (2012) and others were used.

Research results: Social work training tools include textbooks, teaching aids, diagrams, audio-visual materials and other resources. These tools are the basis of the educational process and play a key role in the formation of professional skills and abilities of students. The main objectives of the teaching tools include increasing the pedagogical effect, forming moral education, ensuring the development of students, providing deep and specific knowledge, familiarization with research methods and assistance in organizing mental activity.

Conclusions: The use of various learning tools in the educational process of social work contributes to the formation of students' necessary professional knowledge and skills, the development of their personality and the improvement of the effectiveness of the educational process. Personality-oriented and developmental learning plays a key role in the training of qualified specialists in the field of social work. Recommendations for improving learning tools include the integration of interactive technologies, updating educational materials and taking into account the individual characteristics of students.

Keywords: Social work, Training manuals, Pedagogical methods, Professional skills, The educational process, Personality-oriented learning, interactive technologies

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Research methods

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The results of the study

Social work training tools include textbooks, teaching aids, diagrams, audio-visual materials and other resources. These tools are the basis of the educational process and play a key role in the formation of professional skills and abilities of students. The main tasks of learning tools 1. Increasing the pedagogical effect: Learning tools contribute to a more effective assimilation of the material by students. The use of various educational resources makes it possible to use different channels of information perception, which

improves understanding and memorization of educational material [2, 4]. For example, the use of interactive textbooks and multimedia presentations can significantly increase students' interest in the learning process.

2. Formation of moral education: During the learning process, students develop moral qualities. The teaching tools include materials aimed at developing students' understanding of social responsibility, moral and ethical standards, which is especially important in the professional activities of social workers [6]. The examples given in textbooks often focus on real-world situations that require moral and ethical solutions.

3. Ensuring the development of students: Learning tools contribute to the development of intellectual, emotional and volitional qualities of students. They stimulate critical thinking, a creative approach to problem solving, and also contribute to the development of empathy and emotional intelligence [5]. Various exercises and case stages allow students to develop analytical thinking and decision-making skills in conditions of uncertainty.

4. Ensuring the depth and specificity of the educational material: The tutorials provide in-depth and specific knowledge of the subject. They include theoretical foundations, methodological recommendations and practical examples, which helps students to better understand and assimilate the material [9]. For example, a detailed description of social work methods and examples of their application in practice contribute to a more complete mastery of the subject.

5. The main source of knowledge: Textbooks and manuals are the main source of knowledge for students. They systematize and structure information, which facilitates the learning process and makes it more focused [8]. The use of trusted and reputable sources ensures that students receive relevant and reliable knowledge.

6. Familiarization with research methods: The textbooks introduce students to the methods of research and the use of scientific sources. This is important for the formation of critical analysis skills and independent scientific work [7]. The inclusion in educational materials of information on modern methods of data collection and analysis, as well as on the methodology of scientific research helps students to develop research competencies.

7. Assistance in organizing mental activity: Learning tools help the teacher in organizing the mental activity of students. They include tasks and exercises aimed at developing logical thinking, the ability to generalize and classify information [10]. For example, logic diagrams and diagrams help students visualize and structure the material being studied, which improves its assimilation.

8. Creating motivation: Textbooks create motivation for the formation of the personality of students. They include motivating elements such as success stories, examples of career growth and achievement of professional goals, which inspires students to actively study and self-development [3]. Motivating texts and visual materials contribute to the formation of students' positive attitude towards their future profession.

9. Artistic and technical design: Textbooks should be aesthetically designed to attract the attention of students. Good artistic and technical design makes educational materials more attractive and convenient to use [4]. High-quality illustrations, graphs and diagrams help to better understand and remember the material.

The learning tools are classified into three groups: 1. Published learning tools: They include government documents, textbooks, textbooks, scientific and fiction literature, periodicals. These materials are the main sources of theoretical knowledge and provide a systematic study of the subject. Published learning tools play a key role in the formation of basic knowledge and skills necessary for professional activity.

2. Visual aids: They include documents and visual aids on social work. These materials help to visualize complex concepts and processes, making them more understandable to students. Visual aids such as posters, models, diagrams and diagrams contribute to better assimilation of the material through the use of visual images.

3. Audiovisual media: They include educational films, filmstrips, phonograms, television programs and computer equipment. These tools allow you to diversify the learning process and make it more interactive and interesting. Audiovisual materials help students better memorize information and develop analysis and synthesis skills. Thus, the use of various learning tools in the educational process of social work contributes to the formation of students' necessary professional knowledge and skills, the development of their personality and the improvement of the effectiveness of the educational process. A special place in the educational system of Azerbaijan today is occupied by Personality-oriented education, which is aimed at developing students' knowledge, skills, intelligence, will, emotions and other cognitive properties.

The effectiveness of such training increases if a number of conditions are met: Accessibility and complexity of the material

The educational material should be accessible to understanding, but at the same time contain elements of complexity in order to stimulate the intellectual development of students. This suggests that the material should correspond to the level of training of students, but at the same time be complex enough to arouse interest and the need for additional efforts to master it [1, 4]. For example, using complex but understandable tasks helps students develop critical thinking skills and an analytical approach to problem solving.

Interest in the learning process

The learning process should be understandable and interesting for students. This is achieved using a variety of teaching methods, interactive technologies and materials that correspond to the interests and needs of students [5, 6]. An interesting and exciting learning process contributes to a deeper immersion of students in the learning material, increases their motivation and active participation in the educational process.

A balanced combination of difficulty and feasibility of tasks

Tasks should be difficult, but doable, which gives students confidence in their abilities. This means that

learning tasks should be challenging, but realistic enough to be completed [3, 7]. This approach helps students develop their abilities, overcome difficulties and feel satisfied with the results achieved.

Theoretical conclusions and generalizations

Attention should be paid not only to the factual material, but also to theoretical conclusions and generalizations. This allows students not only to memorize facts, but also to understand their interrelationships, build logical chains and draw their own conclusions [8]. This approach contributes to a deeper and more meaningful assimilation of educational material.

The optimal learning rate

The pace of learning should be optimal for each specific class, so as not to overload students and maintain their interest. This implies a flexible approach to planning the educational process, considering individual characteristics and the level of training of students [2]. The right pace of learning helps to avoid overloads, while maintaining a high level of learning activity and interest.

Formation of skills and abilities

In the process of learning social work, the following basic skills and abilities are formed: Material analysis The ability to analyze material, identify significant signs and connections of phenomena is a fundamental skill for social workers. This includes the ability to deeply investigate problems, identify their root causes and build logically sound conclusions [1, 9].

Application of logic circuits

The ability to apply general logical schemes to the analysis of social phenomena helps to systematize information and build structured approaches to solving social problems [4, 7]. For example, the use of diagrams and models makes it possible to better understand and visualize complex social processes.

Differentiation of social facts

The ability to differentiate and link social facts and processes over time contributes to a more accurate understanding of the historical context and dynamics of social change [6]. This is important for developing effective social work strategies and understanding cause-and-effect relationships.

Comparison of phenomena

The ability to compare phenomena and identify their common and distinctive features helps to better understand the diversity of social phenomena and find optimal solutions for various situations [2, 5]. Comparative analysis contributes to the development of critical thinking and the ability to evaluate alternative approaches.

Commenting on the material

The ability to comment on the material orally and in writing, to give short and detailed answers to questions is an important skill for future social workers. This includes the ability to express your thoughts clearly and logically, argue your position and interact with different audiences [8].

Preparation of reports and abstracts

The ability to prepare information, reports, abstracts, and political information requires skills in data

collection, analysis, and presentation. This helps students develop the research and communication skills necessary for professional activities [3, 10].

Making a plan

The ability to plan, write term papers and theses, and highlight the main points of explanation is a key skill for academic and professional activities. This includes the skills of planning, structuring information and formulating clear and reasoned conclusions [4, 7].

Development of students' thinking and speech

The development of students' thinking, and speech is closely related to the formation of skills and abilities. Knowledge and skills are interrelated, and their development requires a systematic approach and consideration of individual characteristics of students. For example, critical thinking develops through systematic analysis and synthesis of information, and developed speech helps to communicate and interact effectively with different audiences [5, 9]. There are two points of view on the formation of skills and habits, as well as their relationship. The first point of view (Y. K. Babansky, I. Y. Lerner, N. A. Loshkareva) characterizes skills as a means of conscious possession of some kind of activity. A habit is a skill that has reached the degree of automation. The skill is gradually becoming a habit. So, the organization of work with a textbook that has a specific type of skills and corresponding skills in the educational process at the same time (capturing the main idea, explaining the essence of concepts, analyzing and systematizing the material, drawing up a plan, reading diagrams, diagrams and other schematic materials, etc.). The second point of view concerns working with texts and audiovisual sources acquired by listening (listening to a teacher's lecture, a student's report, assimilation of information transmitted on radio and television, etc.). It is also worth paying attention to the formation of library and bibliographic skills. Based on certain habits, even broader, generalized skills are developed, as well as a high degree of mastery of the way of activity. The skill is acquired based on knowledge about the method of activity and variable tasks. Another point of view (Y. N. Kabanova-Meller) defines the ability to possess knowledge about the way of activity as the initial stage of habit formation. Both points of view differ in the question of the relationship between skills and habits and in assessing their role in the development of students.

Classification of the basic skills formed in the learning process

In the methodological literature, the skills formed in the process of learning social work are conventionally grouped as follows:

1. **** Analysis of the material****: The ability to analyze the material, identify the essential signs and connections of the phenomenon and manifestation, define concepts
2. ****Separation of the content of the material****: Deductive application of a general logical scheme to the analysis of same-sex phenomena and manifestations (for example, the use of a logical scheme for studying material on social work)
3. ****Differentiation and linking of social facts and processes****: The ability to make tables and graphs

4. ****Display and interpretation of events****: Display and interpretation of events within the spatial boundaries necessary for analysis

5. ****Comparison of phenomena and manifestations****: The ability to compare phenomena and identify their common and distinctive features

6. ****Conclusions based on the comparison of social facts****: Using inductive and deductive mental conclusions to substantiate conclusions and build evidence based on social facts and generalizations

7. ****Commenting on the material****: The ability to comment on the material orally and in writing, give short and detailed answers to questions, give feedback on the response of friends, etc.

8. ****Preparation of information, reports, abstracts****: The ability to prepare information, reports, abstracts, political information

9. ****Planning and writing a thesis****: The ability to make a summary plan, highlight the main points of the teacher's explanation, take quotations from literature and use information and survey literature. The formation of skills and abilities, as well as the development of thinking and speech, occurs in the process of acquiring knowledge. There is a relationship between knowledge and skills.

Knowledge always refers to a certain system of skills and abilities and, in turn, is the basis for the formation of new skills and habits [1, 10]. For the development of knowledge and skills, it is necessary to know which circle of basic knowledge and skills of students should be related to. It should also be borne in mind that the level of development of students' abilities in the group is not the same. Therefore, they should be treated differently [4, 7].

Conclusion

In the process of learning social work, a variety of learning tools are used aimed at developing students' professional knowledge and skills. Personality-oriented and developmental learning promotes the development

of critical thinking, independence and the ability to analyze and synthesize. This training also ensures the formation of emotional and volitional qualities necessary for professional activity in the social sphere. The study showed that the use of various learning tools can improve the quality of the educational process and increase the level of training of future social workers. The importance of a systematic approach and considering the individual characteristics of students in teaching social work cannot be overestimated. In conclusion, it can be noted that effective social work training requires the integration of various teaching methods and tools, as well as considering the individual characteristics of students. Personality-oriented and developmental learning, regular updating of educational materials and the use of a variety of educational resources create optimal conditions for the training of qualified specialists in the field of social work.

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